

Process to Implement Research Relative Value Unit in Clinical Practice

Lisa R. Treviño, PhD¹, Manish Singh, MD, FACS², and Sohail Rao, MD, MA, DPhil^{3,4}

¹Vice President for Research, DHR Health, 5501 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539 and Vice President for Research Operations, DHR Health Institute for Research & Development, 5323 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6204-2124>

²Chief Executive Officer, DHR Health, 5501 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539

³Executive Vice President, DHR Health, 5501 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539 and President & Chief Executive Officer, DHR Health Institute for Research & Development, 5323 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5027-9992>

⁴Correspondence should be addressed to: Sohail Rao, MD, MA, DPhil., DHR Health Institute for Research & Development, 5323 S. McColl Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539. Tel: (956) 362-2387.

E-mail: s.rao@dhr-rgv.com.

Table 1. Research RVU Model Calculations. Sample schedule of assessments per clinical trial visit is illustrated. The total time per study visit is estimated prior to initiation of study. Each study visit is assigned the closest E&M code that incorporates estimated visit time (in minutes) and patient acuity into account. The rRVU is determined based on E&M code as estimated Medicare reimbursement

STUDY ASSESSMENTS	PHYSICIAN INVOLVEMENT	PHYSICIAN TIME (MINUTES) PER VISIT				
		SCREENING VISIT	VISIT 2	VISIT 3	VISIT 4	VISIT 5
Informed Consent	Yes	22	0	0	0	0
Determination of study eligibility	Yes	10	10	0	0	0
Demographics and Medical History	-	0	0	0	0	0
Physical Examination	Yes	10	10	0	0	0
Height, Weight, BMI, Waist Circumference	-	0	0	0	0	0
Pregnancy Test	-	0	0	0	0	0
Fasting multiparametric MRI Scan	Yes	1	1	0	0	0
Fibroscan	Yes	1	0	0	0	0
HbA1c	Yes	1	1	0	0	0
Fasting blood samples for fibrosis biomarkers	Yes	1	1	0	0	1
Fasting serum sample for OWL metabolomics	Yes	1	1	0	0	0
Fasting plasma for free amino acids	Yes	1	1	0	0	0
Fasting lipid profile	Yes	1	1	0	0	1
Fasting blood glucose	Yes	1	1	0	1	1
Review of the weekly hunger and Satiety VAS	-	0	0	0	0	0
Review activity pattern with participant	-	0	5	5	5	5
Record adverse events	Yes	10	10	10	10	10
Record concomitant medications	-	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL TIME		60	42	15	16	18
ESTIMATED E&M CODE		99205	99204	99213	99202	99202
ESTIMATED rRVU		3.17	2.43	0.97	0.93	0.93

Table 2. Creation of research-specific billing codes. To generate a research-specific billing code which ensures that a patient’s insurance will not be billed, we create an alphanumeric code that is 7 to 10 characters in length. First three characters reflect study name, followed by two characters that reflect visit number and/or designation, followed by the last two digits of the specific CPT® code

STUDY NAME	VISIT NUMBER OR DESIGNATION	CPT® CODE	RESEARCH BILLING CODE
EET Pharmaceuticals	Screening Visit	99205	EETSV05
BTP Biologics	Visit 2	99204	BTPV204
HCC Phase 2	Close Out Visit	99213	HCCCV13

Figure 1. Workflow to obtaining rRVU for clinical study visits. At every clinical study visit, research staff determines if physician or provider is required to perform the indicated assessment in the schedule of activities in a given clinical trial. Once it is determined that the physician is required to conduct the assessment, the appropriate time is estimated per assessment. The total time in each visit is determined and linked to a specific evaluation and management code (E&M) which is then translated to a five-digit current procedural and terminology (CPT®) code. The rRVU is then assigned based on specific CPT® code

